

Supplementary information

A high-quality draft genome for *Melaleuca alternifolia* (tea tree) - a new platform for evolutionary genomics of myrtaceous terpene-rich species

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Syntenic maps

Supplementary figure 1 Syntenic Map (SynMap) of the predicted coding sequences (CDS) of *M. alternifolia* and *C. citriodora* with a syntenic path assembly. The *M. alternifolia* scaffolds (y-axis) are ordered according to their synteny to the *C. citriodora* chromosomes (x-axis), which are ordered numerically. The grey area at the end of the x-axis represents the remaining scaffolds of the *C. citriodora* assembly.

y-axis organism: *Melaleuca alternifolia* (v1.2)

x-axis organism: *Populus trichocarpa* (v3)

Supplementary figure 2 SynMap of the *M. alternifolia* CDS (y-axis) aligned to the *P. trichocarpa* CDS (x-axis) based on syntenic regions in their genomes. The grey area at the end of the x-axis represents the remaining scaffolds of the *P. trichocarpa* assembly.

Genome alignments

Supplementary figure 3 Whole-genome alignment of *M. alternifolia* and *E. grandis* using Mummerplot. Forward matches are shown in red, while reverse matches are displayed in blue.

OrthoFinder results

Supplementary table 1 Overall statistics created by OrthoFinder for the comparison of *Arabidopsis thaliana*, *A. lyrata*, *Corymbia citriodora*, *Eucalyptus grandis*, *M. alternifolia*, *Populus trichocarpa*, *Salix purpurea* and *Vitis vinifera*.

Attribute	Count
Number of species	8
Number of genes	272,343
Number of genes in orthogroups	248,528
Number of unassigned genes	23,815
Percentage of genes in orthogroups	91.3
Percentage of unassigned genes	8.7
Number of orthogroups	29,672
Number of species-specific orthogroups	4,386
Number of genes in species-specific orthogroups	16,828
Percentage of genes in species-specific orthogroups	6.2
Mean orthogroup size	8.4
Median orthogroup size	7
Number of orthogroups with all species present	10,982
Number of single-copy orthogroups	1,762

Supplementary table 2 Species-specific statistics for orthogroup assignments by OrthoFinder.

	<i>A. lyrata</i>	<i>A. thaliana</i>	<i>C. citriodora</i>	<i>E. grandis</i>	<i>M. alternifolia</i>	<i>P. trichocarpa</i>	<i>S. purpurea</i>	<i>V. vinifera</i>
Number of genes	31,073	27,654	35,632	36,349	37,226	34,699	37,865	31,845
Number of genes in orthogroups	29,283	26,217	33,095	31,762	33,768	32,224	35,073	27,106
Number of unassigned genes	1,790	1,437	2,537	4,587	3,458	2,475	2,792	4,739
Percentage of genes in orthogroups	94.2	94.8	92.9	87.4	90.7	92.9	92.6	85.1
Percentage of unassigned genes	5.8	5.2	7.1	12.6	9.3	7.1	7.4	14.9
Number of orthogroups containing species	17,772	17,446	18,200	17,530	17,600	16,862	16,859	16,046
Percentage of orthogroups containing species	59.9	58.8	61.3	59.1	59.3	56.8	56.8	54.1
Number of species-specific orthogroups	453	160	474	525	991	253	521	1,009
Number of genes in species-specific orthogroups	1,594	521	1,599	1,665	4,828	1,011	1,721	3,889
Percentage of genes in species-specific orthogroups	5.1	1.9	4.5	4.6	13.0	2.9	4.5	12.2

